

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: I122ra2.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of I122ra2 as a candidate
9 gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

11 1. Fachi, J.L., Di Luccia, B., Gilfillan, S., Chang, H.W., Song, C., Cheng, J., Cella, M., Vinolo, M.A.,
12 Gordon, J.I. and Colonna, M., 2024. Deficiency of IL-22-binding protein enhances the ability of the gut
13 microbiota to protect against enteric pathogens. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*,
14 121(19), p.e2321836121.